

Hyperspectral image compression using convolutional neural networks with local spectral transforms and non-uniform sample normalisation

Presented by Sebastià Mijares i Verdú

Co authors: Johannes Ballé, Valero Laparra, Joan Bartrina-Rapesta, Miguel Hernández-Cabronero, Joan Serra-Sagristà

Summary

What is this presentation all about?

1 Challenges in hyperspectral data compression we aim to solve

2 ML compression precedents and proposed method

PSNR rate-distortion performance of our proposed method and other codecs on the AVIRIS test set.

3 Performance of our method

Original Proposed model 320 filters (60,97dB PSNR, 0.157bps) 4-band KLT+JPEG 2000 (60,66dB PSNR, 0.16bps) 224-band KLT+JPEG 2000 (75,40dB PSNR, 0.22bps)

4 Next phases of development

Motivation and related work

Motivation and related work

Hyperpsectral image compression and ML image compression

Motivation and related work

Hyperpsectral image compression and ML image compression

High spectral correlation

Article

Multispectral Transforms Using Convolution Neural Networks for Remote Sensing Multispectral Image Compression

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Convolution Neural Network based lossy compression of hyperspectral images

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Article

Reduced-Complexity End-to-End Variational Autoencoder for on Board Satellite Image Compression

Vinicius Alves de Oliveira^{1,2,*}, Marie Chabert¹, Thomas Oberlin³, Charly Poulliat¹, Mickael Bruno⁴, Christophe Latry⁴, Mikael Carlavan⁵, Simon Henrot⁵, Frederic Falzon⁵ and Roberto Camarero⁶

RQCSNet: A deep learning approach to quantized compressed sensing of remote sensing images

Alireza Mirrashid | Ali-Asghar Beheshti Shirazi

Numerous contributions on ML remote sensing data compression

Article

Spectral-Spatial Feature Partitioned Extraction Based on CNN for Multispectral Image Compression

Fanqiang Kong¹, Kedi Hu^{1,*}, Yunsong Li², Dan Li¹ and Shunmin Zhao¹

2D compression (JPEG 2000, CCSDS 122.0)

1D+2D compression (KLT followed by JPEG 2000, CCSDS 122.0)

Motivation and related work

Hyperpsectral image compression and ML image compression

High spectral correlation

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RQCSNet: A deep learning approach to quantized compressed sensing of remote sensing images

Alireza Mirrashid | Ali-Asghar Beheshti Shirazi

A few contributions on reduced-complexity designs

These remain more costly to run than established conventional methods based on CNN

Fanqiang Kong¹, Kedi Hu^{1,*}, Yunsong Li², Dan Li¹ and Shunmin Zhao¹

2D compression (JPEG 2000, CCSDS 122.0)

1D+2D compression (KLT followed by JPEG 2000, CCSDS 122.0)

Our method

Our method

Band cluster compression

Complexity of linear spectral transform is $O(n^2)$ on the number of bands

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Complexity of linear spectral transform is $O(n^2)$ on the number of bands

$O(n^2)$

Partition in clusters of k bands and apply linear transform

$O(nk)$

Our method

Neural network architecture

Our network requires:

- ~x5 fewer operations than the baseline for 4-band image compression
- ~40 more operations than KLT+JPEG 2000 for 4-band image compression
- ~20 more operations than KLT+JPEG 2000 for 224-band image compression

Results

Results

Compression performance

PSNR rate-distortion performance of our proposed method and other codecs on the AVIRIS test set.

PSNR rate-distortion performance of the Ballé *et al.* 2018 architecture and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in batches of 3 channels on AVIRIS images.

Results

Visual comparison

Original

Proposed model 320 filters (60,97dB
PSNR, 0.157bps)

4-band KLT+JPEG 2000 (60,66dB
PSNR, 0.16bps)

224-band KLT+JPEG 2000 (75,40dB
PSNR, 0.22bps)

Original

Proposed model 320 filters (60,97dB
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PSNR, 0.22bps)

Results

Visual comparison at $\sim 0.5\text{bps}$

Results

Visual comparison at ~ 0.5 bps

4-band KLT

Original

224-band KLT

Our models

Results

Visual comparison in low variance channels

4-band KLT

224-band KLT

Original

Our models

Range-adaptive normalisation makes low-variance and/or noisy band reconstruction more stable

Results

Runtime test

Codec	Average image compression time (s)
4-band KLT+JPEG 2000	24,8981
224-band KLT+JPEG 2000	60,1758
224-band JPEG 2000	4,4465
Our model (CPU, 192-filters)	18,8076
Our model (CPU+TPU, 192-filters)	1,9191

Take these with a pinch of salt!

We carried out this runtime test on a 4-core Intel Core i5 CPU. Our implementation of JPEG 2000 was Kakadu, and our implementation of KLT is in Java (suboptimal runtime). Our models were implemented in Python (Tensorflow). All our codecs stored compressed images to disk (SSD).

These are preliminary results in lieu of a more controlled experiment.

Google-developed TPU

In our experiment we used Coral as a TPU accelerator for our models. It sped up our models' runtime x10 and developers claim it can perform 2TFLOP/W.

Results

Runtime test

Future development

Future development

Improvements on spectral transform

Full linear spectral transform

Pairwise Orthogonal Transform for Spectral Image Coding

Ian Blanes, *Student Member, IEEE*, and Joan Serra-Sagristà, *Member, IEEE*

IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING, VOL. 49, NO. 3, MARCH 2011

Multi-level spectral transform

$$f(B_{i-k}, \dots, B_i) = \hat{B}_i$$

Progressive spectral decorrelation

Non-linear spectral transform

Thank you for your time!

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with local spectral transforms and non-uniform sample normalisation

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8th OBPDC 2022, Athens, September 30th 2022